

THE IMPORTANCE OF ANCESTRAL HERITAGE IN RAISING FAMILY SPIRITUALITY

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ANNOTATSIYA

oila oila oila

Kalit soʻzlarga : oila, oila bu tarbiyaviy maskan

"National Idea, Fundamentals of Spirituality and Legal Education"

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The family is a small group of people whose marriage or blood-kinship ties are based on a common way of life, moral responsibility, and mutual support. The concept of community and family are interrelated. Every family is formed according to the requirements of society. The development of a society is directly related to the degree to which it is formed in the social, economic and spiritual image of the families that exist in its bosom. The family is the most important environment for the upbringing of a child, in which the character, including will, personality, character and worldview, which are important for the development of the individual, is formed. In the East, family upbringing has long been highly valued. The state's care for the family is reflected in the adopted laws and decisions. The establishment of family research and practice centers in the country is a vivid evidence of this.

The concept of family began with the development of the spiritual and enlightenment consciousness of this young generation. To do this, we must pay special attention to the upbringing of our children growing up in a family. That is why it is not said in vain that the family is a small Motherland within the Motherland; The family has always been considered great and sacred, and it is a blessing to grow up in a holy place with a good upbringing and perfection. Our family scientific, cultural and educational heritage; our customs and traditions; solidarity and unity are sacred values at all times. In order to know the family, we must first pay special attention to the history of its creation. Nowadays, the fact that many young families are on the verge of divorce is also a topical issue. What is the origin of this and what is the reason for it

?, The reason for this is one. The inexperience and irresponsibility of young people is one of the reasons for this. To prevent the number of divorces from increasing, young people need to be well educated in family life. In order to have a family experience, we need to follow the advice of older people and it is permissible.

It is not for nothing that it is said, "An old man has a housewife."

In this regard, our President is taking a lot of measures and making many decisions. An example of this is the Constitution of the Republic of Uzbekistan, which states and specifies the family: in particular, Article 63 of Chapter 14 of our Constitution states that the family is the basic unit of society and has the right to be under state protection.

Since the creation of mankind, the word family has a deep meaning. It is very important to have a high level of understanding and experience to understand the essence of that deep content. In order to achieve a high position in society and in our own family, we must first have a high position in the family circle. In the family circle, the right person can always find his place. As in all spheres, a number of important changes are taking place in education and in the organization of family upbringing. In the current situation, there are many difficulties in organizing the upbringing of children in the family.

These include:

- Insufficient awareness of parents of pedagogical knowledge;
- Decreased interest of school-age children in reading as a result of economic difficulties during adolescence, in the transition of modern media, including telephones, to social life, as well as their positive impact on children's fiction. a significant decrease in interest in winter;
- One of the saddest and most harmful habits is the increase in the number of violent views on the Internet, which leads to a feeling of cruelty and aggression in children.

In order to get rid of these harmful habits as soon as possible, we must teach our children to use their free time effectively so that our children can contribute to the peace and prosperity of our country. For this:

- It is necessary and permissible to teach our children to take a responsible approach to their work as parents;
- responsible decision-making in children's homework;
- not to allow children to be late for training and not to return home on time;

- The need to create opportunities for children to prepare for lessons in any situation;

- - First of all, we need to pay special attention to the skills of children to follow the agenda.

We need to keep an eye on our children at all times, especially to teach them how to use their free time productively. Only then can we achieve the desired result. Moral upbringing also plays an important role in the family. From this we can express and form the highest moral qualities of children - respect for parents and other family members, respect for others, respect for the little ones, humility, diligence, honesty, humanity, justice, conscience, discipline, love. we need to make it clear that it is an important concept to support each other in any situation. Only in this way will mature people who love their country, who respect their parents, who are always able to think ahead, who achieve a lot of success and achievements, who love their profession. Abdullah Avloni says, "Education is for us a matter of life, salvation, or disaster."

That is why we must never face catastrophic situations. To do this, we must always know what the responsibility is and not always lose confidence in ourselves.